

BC-SIM-TR-036

EGSE ICO#4B Report

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1 Introduction

1.1 Scope

In this document we will describe all the tests performed during the recovery of the fourth Instrument Checkout (ICO#04B) for the Spectrometers and Imagers for MPO BepiColombo Integrated Observatory SYStem (SIMBIO-SYS). The checkout session was performed April 24th 2021. For each test it will be presented the pipeline report and, where necessary, a discussion on the detected anomalies.

1.2 Reference Document

[RD.1]	BC-SIM-PL-007-Checkout_04B_Test_Summary_Issue_1 (DOI: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10035541)
[RD.2]	BC-SIM-TN-003 - Reports and Notes Layout and Flow
[RD.3]	BC-SIM-TR-XXX Technical Report - Software User Manual, in preparation;
[RD.4]	BC-SIM-GAF-IC-002_rev12 - SIMBIO-SYS Software Interface Control Document
[RD.5]	BepiColombo FOP data package 3.1
[RD.6]	BC-ASD-SP-00176_1_4 SIMBIO URD
[RD.7]	BC-SIM-GAF-MA-002 10 001 - SIMBIO-SYS User Manual
[RD.8]	BC-SIM-TN-006_-_simClean_-_Telemetry_Filter_Tool (DOI: https://doi.org/10.20371/INAF/TechRep/103);
[RD.9]	BC-SIM-TR-016_-_Anomalies_in_Packet_Sorting (DOI: https://doi.org/10.20371/INAF/TechRep/176);
[RD.10]	BC-SIM-TN-011_-_simResort_User_Manual_-_Version_1.0.0 (DOI: https://doi.org/10.20371/INAF/TechRep/184)

1.3 Acronyms

APID	Application Process Identifier
CSV	Comma Separated Values
FPA	Focal Plane Assembly
HK	Housekeeping
HRIC	High spatial Resolution Imaging Channel
LBF	Low Frequency Behavior
ME	Main Electronics
NECP	Near Earth Commissioning Phase
dNECP	delta Near Earth Commissioning Phase
PDS	Planetary Data System
PE	Proximity Electronics
PNG	Portable Network Graphics
PSC	Packet Sequence Control
SIMBIO-SYS	Spectrometers and Imagers for MPO BepiColombo Integrated Observatory SYStem
SSC	Source Sequence Count
STC	STereo imaging Channel
TBW	To Be Written
TC	Telecommand
TM	Telemetry
VIHI	Visible and Hyper-spectral Imaging channel
XML	eXtensible Markup Language

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1.4 Document Format and Repository

This document is compliant with the SIMBIO-SYS Report and Note Layout and Flow [RD.2] and will be archived on the SIMBIO-SYS ZENODO community (<https://zenodo.org/communities/?p=SIMBIO-SYS>), on the INAF Open Access repository and the SIMBIO-SYS team Archive.

1.5 Test Plan

The ICO#4B test was planned to be executed on one day based on the tests described in [RD.1].

ID	Test Description	Start	Stop
1	VIHI Performance Test	2021-04-24T08:00:00.00Z	2021-04-24T08:25:00.00Z
2	Interference Test	2021-04-24T08:35:00.00Z	2021-04-24T09:56:00.00Z

Table 1: Test Schedule.

1.6 Report Schema

For each test, the report will be formed by four sections created by an automatic procedure:

- a summary of all the data produced during that test;
- a report with the events and telecommand acknowledgments;
- a report of the PE events;
- a check on the lost packets.

The report includes even two sections with a comparison between the commanded TCs and the data results. Eventual problems or discrepancies will be discussed.

The complete Sections list defined for each test is shown in Table 2 and described in the subsections below.

Session #	Session Name
1	Telecommands
2	Data Procedure
3	Events Check
4	PE Event
5	Lost packets
6	Telecommand Check
7	Discussion

Table 2: Section structure defined for each Test.

1.6.1 Telecommands

In this Section, the telecommands used for the test will be reported. For each telecommand an analysis and an evaluation of the produced data will be performed.

1.6.2 Data Produced

In this Section, a table with the data produced will be reported. The output files consist in two different types of CSVs (one for the diagnostic housekeeping and one with all the housekeeping parameters related to a single image) and a file containing the image in binary format. All data are compliant to the PDS4 format,

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which means that they include an XML file with all the parameters of each acquisition, both considering as source the instrument or the spacecraft. A complete description of the file structure and the folder tree is reported in [RD.3]. For each image it is present an additional file in PNG format as a quick preview. In the summary schema it will be reported the number and the total size of the following file types:

- Diagnostic HKs
- Acquisition HKs;
- Images

1.6.3 Events Check

In the events check section it will be reported:

- all the negative telecommand acknowledgments,
- the rejected telecommands, TM(1,2),
- the failed telecommands, TM(1,8).

For each negative event (rejected, failed or ignored telecommand), all the information about the telecommand, mnemonic name, description, time of execution, and all associated parameters are reported. For each event it is reported a list for the low severity TM(5,2), medium severity TM(5,3) and high severity TM(5,4) errors with a description of the event.

The complete list of events and telecommand acknowledgments is reported into the Event file stored in each test folder. All the information relative to an event or a telecommand acknowledgments are from [RD.4].

1.6.4 PE Events

From an automatic analysis of the diagnostic HK, a list of the negative event alerts, sent by the PE, is created. Each alert is reported with the associated decimal ID and with its complete description. All the information relative to a PE events refers to [RD.4].

1.6.5 Lost Packets

The automatic check on the lost packets is performed using the Packet Sequence Control (PSC) number (see [RD.4]). The PSC is a serial number associated with the TM packets and follows a different enumeration for different APID. A list of the used APID is reported in the following table:

APID	Description
801	TC Verification
804	HK Reports
807	Event Reports
828	HRIC Data High Priority
844	STC Data High Priority
860	VIHI Data High Priority
870	HRIC Data Low Priority
892	STC Data Low Priority
908	VIHI Data Low Priority

Table 3: List of the APIDs associated to each dataflow.

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The PSC number is stored in 14 bits. This means that the maximum value is 16383. After that, the counter restart from 0.

NB: A manual check-in is required in order to evaluate if some packets are lost at the beginning and the end of the acquisition. The automatic check detects only holes in the PSC sequence.

1.6.6 Telecommand Check

In this Section it is checked that the ME and the PE have executed all received telecommand.

1.6.7 Test Results

In this Section we will discuss the results, the discrepancies, and the errors if they are present.

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2 Preprocessing

The TM file downloaded from the EDDS server has been preprocessed using the simClean tools [RD.8] to remove the duplicate HK and the duplicated science packets due to the reception of the same one by different antennas.

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3 ICO#4B Results Analysis

3.1 General consideration

With reference to Table 4, we report the following quality table:

ID	Test Name	Test result
01	VIHI Performance Test	
02	Interference Test	

Table 4: Quality table.

for which we use the following color keys in the last column:

Red: test failed;

Yellow: test partially passed;

Green: Test passed.

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3.2 VIHI Performance Test

3.2.1 Test Scope

The test will be devoted to the accurate description and understanding of the Dark Current management.

3.2.2 Test Execution

Time Frame: 2021-04-24T08:00:00.00Z ÷ 2021-04-24T08:25:00.00Z.

In Table 5 the initial status of the instrument is reported:

INSTRUMENT INITIAL STATUS			
ME	HRIC	STC	VIHI
OFF	OFF	OFF	OFF

Table 5: Instrument status before the VIHI Performance Test.

3.2.3 Science

Concerning the Science TCs, the following science session has been performed.

ID	SSC	Duration	Mode	Repetition Time [s]	Expected Acquisition	Expected Frame
1	1834	3 seconds	Continuous	0.13	24	24
2	1835	3.01 seconds	Continuous	0.13	24	24
3	1836	3.02 seconds	Continuous	0.16	20	20
4	1837	2.98 seconds	Continuous	0.3	12	12
5	1840	2.98 seconds	Continuous	0.3	12	12
6	1841	2.98 seconds	Continuous	0.3	8	8
7	1842	2.98 seconds	Continuous	0.3	6	6
8	1843	2.98 seconds	Continuous	0.3	4	4
9	1844	2.98 seconds	Continuous	0.3	6	6
10	1845	2.98 seconds	Continuous	0.3	2	2
11	1846	2.98 seconds	Continuous	0.3	3	3
12	1847	2.98 seconds	Continuous	0.3	2	2
12	---	36 seconds	---	---	123	123

Table 6: Description of the TC used during VIHI Functional Test.

Table 6 describes the duration and the number of images and frames expected for each TCs commanded during the Performance Test.

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3.2.4 Data Produced

Bundle Miscellaneous			
File	CSV		
		#	2
		Size	793.7 kB

Bundle Raw VIHI			
File	CSV		
		#	123
		Size	176.9 kB
DAT			
		#	123
		Size	13.9 MB

Table 7: Data produced during the VIHI Performance Test.

3.2.5 ME Events

None.

3.2.6 PE Events

None.

3.2.7 Lost Packets

Type of Packets	#	Note
Telecommand Verification	68	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
HK Report	1156	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
Event/Anomaly Report	8	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
VIHI low Priority	3167	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
VIHI high Priority	0	[Lost Packet(s) 0]

Table 8: Packets and lost packet report for the VIHI Performance Test.

3.2.8 TC Check

Telecommand Status	#
Accepted	34
Executed	34
Rejected	0
Failed	0

Table 9: Comparison between data commanded and produced for the VIHI Performance Test.

3.2.9 Discussion

Produced output is in line with what expected.

The details are reported in Table 10 with information from section 3.2.3 and 3.2.4.

	Commanded	From TM
Images	123	123
Science Sessions	12	12

Table 10: Comparison between data commanded and produced for the VIHI Performance Test.

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3.3 Interference test

3.3.1 Test Scope

The aim of this test is to evaluate if and how the cameras (i.e., HRIC and STC) detector reset fluctuations change with respect to the Repetition Time parameter contained in their Science TC.

In addition, the test will indicate if the operativity of the VIHI channel influences or not such a fluctuation.

3.3.2 Test Execution

Time Frame: 2021-04-24T08:35:00.00Z ÷ 2021-04-24T09:56:00.00Z

In Table 11 is reported the initial status of the instrument:

INSTRUMENT INITIAL STATUS			
ME	HRIC	STC	VIHI
OFF	OFF	OFF	OFF

Table 11: Instrument status before the Interference Test.

3.3.3 Science

3.3.3.1 HRIC

ID	SSC	Duration	Mode	Repetition Time [s]	Expected Acquisition	Expected Frame
1	997	5 minutes	Continuous	1.0	300	300
2	999	7 minutes	Continuous	1.5	280	280
3	1011	5 minutes	Continuous	1.0	300	300
4	1013	7 minutes and 1 second	Continuous	1.5	281	281
4	---	24 minutes and 1 second	---	---	1161	1161

Table 12: Description of the science TC used by HRIC during the Interference Test.

3.3.3.2 STC

ID	SSC	Duration	Mode	Repetition Time [s]	Expected Acquisition	Expected Frame
1	996	12 minutes	Continuous	1.0	720	720
2	1010	12 minutes and 2 seconds	Continuous	1.0	722	722
2	---	24 minutes and 2 seconds	---	---	1442	1442

Table 13: Description of the science TC used by STC during the Interference Test.

3.3.3.3 VIHI

ID	SSC	Duration	Mode	Repetition Time [s]	Expected Acquisition	Expected Frame
1	1009	12 minutes	Continuous	0.5	1440	1440
1	---	12 minutes	---	---	1440	1440

Table 14: Description of the science TC used by VIHI during the Interference Test.

In Figure 1, which is shown the Interference test timeline, underlies a first phase with the interference of the two imaging channels and a second one where all the channels are commanded together.

Figure 1: TC Timeline for the Interference test.

3.3.4 Data Produced

Bundle Miscellaneous			
File	CSV		
		#	4
		Size	309.6 kB

Bundle Raw HRIC			
File	CSV		
		#	1161
		Size	1.1 MB
	DAT		
		#	1161
		Size	152.2 MB

Bundle Raw STC			
File	CSV		
		#	1442
		Size	1.3 MB
	DAT		
		#	1442
		Size	25.0 MB

Bundle Raw VIHI			
File	CSV		
		#	1440
		Size	2.1 MB
	DAT		
		#	1440
		Size	25.7 MB

Table 15: Data produced during the Interference Test.

3.3.5 ME Error

Severity Level	#
Low Severity Error	1
Medium Severity Error	0
High Severity Error	0

Table 16: ME errors during the Interference Test grouped by severity.

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3.3.5.1 Low Severity Error

- [2021-04-24T09:40:10.563] - TM(5,2) - [APID 807] - Event 40800 - HK discarded due to SpW error on link from the specified channel.

3.3.6 PE Error

	#
HRIC PE negative event(s)	0
STC PE negative event(s)	0
VIHI PE negative event(s)	1

Table 17: Pe Errors during The Interference Test grouped by Channel.

3.3.6.1 VIHI PE Errors

- [2021-04-24T09:40:12.208] VIHI TC length not correct (4)

3.3.7 Lost Packets

Type of Packets	#	Note
Telecommand Verification	94	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
HK Report	645	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
Event/Anomaly Report	22	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
HRIC low Priority	2322	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
STC low Priority	1442	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
VIHI low Priority	1440	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
HRIC high Priority	0	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
STC high Priority	0	[Lost Packet(s) 0]
VIHI high Priority	0	[Lost Packet(s) 0]

Table 18: Packets and lost packet report for the Interference Test.

3.3.8 TC Check

Telecommand Status	#
Accepted	47
Executed	45
Refuted	0
Failed	2

Table 19: Comparison between data commanded and produced for the Interference Test.

3.3.8.1 Failed Telecommands

- [2021-04-24T09:09:10.038] - TM(1,8) - [APID 801] - Event N/A - Telecommand Execution Failure [Failure ID: 7, APID: 812, Sequence n. 1003]
- [2021-04-24T09:09:15.038] - TM(1,8) - [APID 801] - Event N/A - Telecommand Execution Failure [Failure ID: 40011, APID: 812, Sequence n. 1004]

3.3.9 Discussion

In the telemetry some errors are present (see Sessions 3.3.5, 3.3.6, and 3.3.8), but the produced output is in line with what is expected.

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The details are reported in Table 20, Table 21, and Table 22 with information from section 3.3.3 and 3.3.4.

3.3.9.1 HRIC

	Commanded	From TM
Images	1161	1161
Science Sessions	4	4

Table 20: Comparison between data commanded and produced by HRIC for the Interference Test.

3.3.9.2 STC

	Commanded	From TM
Images	1442	1442
Science Sessions	2	2

Table 21: Comparison between data commanded and produced by STC for the Interference Test.

3.3.9.3 VIHI

	Commanded	From TM
Images	1440	1440
Science Sessions	1	1

Table 22: Comparison between data commanded and produced by VIHI for the Interference Test.

4 Summary

ID	Test description	Test Last	Science Sessions	Data from TLM [Mb]							# Images			Failure									
				HK	HRIC LP	STC LP	VIHI LP	HRIC HP	STC HP	VIHI HP	HRIC	STC	VIHI	HRIC			STC			VIHI			
														TC	ME	PE	TC	ME	PE	TC	ME	PE	
01	VIHI Performance Test	36s	12	0.18	0	0	13.9	0	0	0	0	0	123	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
02	Interference Test	1h 21m	10	4.50	152.2	25.0	25.7	0	0	0	1161	1442	1440	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	1	1	
02		1h 21m 36s	22	4.68	152.2	25.0	39.6	0	0	0	1161	1442	1563	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	1	

Table 23: ICO#04B Summary of all the tests.

Data Volume [Mb]	
HRIC	152.2
STC	25.0
VIHI	39.6
	216.8

Table 24: Data volume produced in the ICO#04B